

Maternal health care services utilization amidst Covid-19 lockdown: retrospective study

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Abstract—

Objective: The objective was to find the changes in maternal health care utilization.

Design: Retrospective design was adopted.

Setting: Study was conducted in Damak, Nepal.

Methods: Data from four hospitals was retrieved for fiscal year 2076/77 (July 14,2019 - June 14 2020). Trend analysis was done.

Results : Study showed a decline in utilization of overall maternal health care during the months of Lockdown The utilization of antenatal care services has declined in the beginning of Lockdown but shows an increasing trend in the month of May-June. The number of Normal deliveries has declining trend since the beginning of Lockdown. The number of Caeserean Section declined during (March 14-April 12) and slightly increased in Bhaishak (April 13-May 13), but reduced again in the month of Jestha (may13-June14). The number of permanent family planning service use reduced in Chaitra (March 14-April 12), increased very slightly in Bhaishak(April 13-May 13), and declined again in the month of Jestha(may13-June14). The utilization of temporary family planning method and immunization has increased in the later month of Lockdown.

Conclusion: This decline in utilization may increase the maternal morbidity and mortality rates.

Keywords: Maternal health services, COVID-19 lockdown, Nepal.

I. INTRODUCTION

Corona virus is the ongoing international pandemic which started at Wuhan City, Hubei province of china on December. The number of infected people with Corona virus worldwide as of July, 2020 is 6,421,255 with mortality up to 3,79,055.¹ In Nepal, first case of Corona Virus was detected in January with increasing cases up to 13248 as of June, 2020.² As a preventive measure, Nepal has been in lockdown since the month of Chaitra,2076 (March,2020).

Maternal Mortality before the pandemic was 229 women/100,000 births according to the 2019 data of Family Welfare Division of Department of Health Services in Nepal. Even with decreasing MMR from 539 in 1996 to 239 in 2016, still 58 per cent of births in Nepal were attended by skilled health personnel before the lockdown.^{2,3} Now, due to movement restrictions, transportation disruptions, and fear of being exposed to the virus, women are facing even more barriers to accessing maternal health care.³

Only around one fourth of women are seeking maternity services at Kathmandu Model Hospital after the lockdown started. Over 60 to 80 women used to visit the hospital's out-patient department every day

prior to the lockdown but now only 15 to 20 women are visiting. Women are visiting the hospitals for only emergency services.

The number of Institutional deliveries have also decreased all over the country, which shows that women are giving birth at home, which might possess a serious threat to mother's and newborn's health. Not only the delivery services, but the records from hospitals nationwide shows that the antenatal and postnatal services are also not being utilized by the women.⁴

The World Health Organization recommends at least 4 ANC visits during pregnancy.⁵ Lack of antenatal care and delivery care possesses risk to both the mother and the baby. Antenatal care is vital for the identification and management of pregnancy related health problems. ANC visits also increases the chances of the mother to get safe deliveries with skilled health care professionals.⁶

Of the total number of maternal deaths, 24 percent occur during or after childbirth and 19 percent in the postnatal period. Now when delivery care and postnatal care has been compromised due to the lockdown, these figures are likely to increase.⁷

Previous data in a study suggests that Ebola outbreak in 2014-15 had led to decrease in the maternal admissions, institutional deliveries which were on ascending trend before epidemic. The number of women taking antenatal care and the immunization levels also decreased significantly. This resulted in a 34 per cent increase in maternal mortality (MMR) and 24 per cent increase infant mortality (IMR). The number of maternal deaths, neonatal deaths and still births which were indirectly caused by the epidemic exceeded the direct epidemic related

death.^{7,8,9}

This study aims to provide data on the usage of maternal health care services on following domains 1) Antenatal care visits 2) Rate of institutional deliveries (Normal Vaginal delivery and Lower Cesarean Section) 3) immunization services 4) Family Planning Services before and during Covid-19 lockdown in Nepal.

Increased risk and relapse to disease is a common threat to pregnancy as seen with several infections.^{10,11} Pregnant female also have increased risk of morbidity and mortality with different infections.^{12,13} Even benign maternal infections can results in severe consequences to both the mother and child and some infections leading to various congenital malformations. The new emerging vaccines and treatment can also be contraindicated in pregnancy which can be a major hindrance to treatment and prevention of new emerging infections in pregnant females.¹⁴

Thus, regular antenatal care is a primary factor to prevent various hazards associated with new emerging infections and risk of maternal to fetus transmission. The risk of lockdown and fear of infection to new outbreak of COVID 19 possess a big burden on the maternal health care system along with various family planning services given by hospitals.

This research aims to determine effect of COVID 19 on maternal visits and care taken by pregnant females, vaccination usage during the lockdown as well as family planning services used. The major purpose of this research is to address the dire situations on maternal health during pandemics. In order to reduce the upcoming issue of risk on maternal and fetal health, family planning and vaccinations, this

study will a approach to policy makers and public health experts to closely work and prevent any decline in the availability of health services to females.

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Design

We conducted retrospective observational study to assess the trend of maternal health care services utilization before and during COVID19 lockdown using routinely reported programme data with total duration of one fiscal year. Quantitative method was approached as the study involved collection of quantitative data from existing data source of hospitals of Damak providing safe motherhood services.

2.2 Setting

This study was done in Damak. It is one of the oldest municipalities in Jhapa District in Province no.1 of Nepal (figure 1) . It is situated between the Ratuwa River in the east and the Maawa River in the west. Mahendra Highway (longest highway of Nepal) crosses this municipality nearly bisecting it. It is the largest city in Jhapa District as well as in Mechi zone with a population of 75,743 in 2011 A.D. There are total 7 hospitals in Damak. Study was done in 4 hospitals Amda hospital, Lifeline hospital, Damak hospital and OM Mechi hospital.

FIGURE 1: Study done in Damak, Jhapa district Nepal

2.3 Data collection:

Data was collected from database of four hospitals providing safe motherhood services of Damak from the start of fiscal year 2019/20 (july 14,2019 to june 14,2020). Data were entered into a dedicated Microsoft Excel database and analyzed using SPSS. Data were also cross validated from respective hospitals in Damak. Data was collected Study population included all women seeking maternal health

service which includes antenatal checkup, family planning visit, normal or cesarean deliveries in all government and private hospitals in Damak. Patient seeking other medical services besides maternity health care service are excluded in this study. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage) was used to analyze the data. Trend analysis was done to see the changes that have occurred due to Covid-19 lockdown.

2.4 Ethical issues and considerations regarding human participants

This research is done from data retrieved from a Hospitals of Damak Municipality, Jhapa and does not involve human participants. Ethical clearance will be obtained from IRC, Nobel Collge. Data was retrieved after taking formal permission from the municipality office.

III. RESULTS

This section deals with the analysis and interpretation of data collected from four hospitals of Damak providing safe motherhood services. Among the four hospitals, one hospital does not provide immunization service. The data was collected from Shrawan-2076 till Jestha 2077 (July 14, 2019- June14, 2020). The date according to Nepali Calendar and English calendar has been mentioned in the data.

3.1 Section 1

The average number of maternal health care services (ANC visits, institutional deliveris, family planning services and immunization) utilized from the fiscal year Shrawan-2076 till Jestha 2077 (July 14, 2019- June 14, 2020).

TABLE 1
THE AVERAGE NUMBER OF MATERNAL HEALTH CARE SERVICES

	Before covid-19 lockdown ((July 17,2019- March 13,2020)		During covid-19 lockdown (March 14,2020- june 14,2020)	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
ANC	2364.1818	689.00970	1377.3333	311.13555
Normal Delivery	363.8182	114.67852	211.6667	64.08068
Caesarean Section	657.2727	175.74532	430.0000	167.68721
Permanent family planing	18.6364	4.80151	18.3333	2.08167
Temporary family planing	11.0000	4.56070	6.3333	4.04145
Immunization	188.2727	99.14241	141.3333	125.12927
TD	151.6364	41.21474	96.3333	21.82506
IUCD	17.3636	14.45180	1.3333	1.52753
Maternal health care services	3772.1818	1014.81484	2282.6667	322.40089

The table 1 shows that the utilization of overall maternal health care services has been reduced during the lockdown period (mean of 3772 before lockdown and 2282 during lockdown).

The utilization of ANC services was reduced during the lockdown period (mean-1377 during lockdown as compared to a mean of 2364 before lockdown). Institutional deliveries (Normal Delivery and Caesarean Section) have also been reduced during the lockdown period. There has been no reduction in utilization of permanent family planning services but the utilization of temporary family planning services has been reduced. Immunization has also been reduced during the lockdown period.

3.2 Section 2

Trend of maternal health care services utilization.

FIGURE 2: Maternal health care service utilization.

The figure 2 shows that the overall utilization of maternal health care services has a declining trend since the beginning of Lockdown (march 14, 2020).

FIGURE 3: Antenatal care utilization

The figure 3 shows the change in ANC services utilization. It shows that the number of women visiting hospitals for antenatal care drastically reduced in the month when the lockdown began and continued to

decline in Bhaishak (April 13, 2020- may 13, 2020). It shows a slight increment in the ANC service utilization in the month of jetha (May 14, 2020-June14, 2020).

FIGURE 4: Number of institutional deliveries.

The figure 4 shows the number of institutional deliveries from the start of Fiscal year 2076/77 (July 17, 2019). The number of Normal deliveries has a declining trend since the beginning of Lockdown. The number of Caeserean Section declined in the month of Chaitra (March 14-April 14) (beginning of Lockdown) and slightly increased in Bhaishak (April 13, 2020-May 13,2020), but reduced again in the month of Jetha (May 14,2020- June 14,2020).

FIGURE 5: Number of family planning methods utilized

The figure 5 shows that the utilization of temporary family planning services reduced when lockdown started and is increased in the later month of Lockdown (May 14,2020- June 14,2020) The number of permanent family planning service used reduced when lockdown started (, increased very slightly in the

second month of Lockdown (April 13-May 13) and declined again in the month of May-June. The number of PPIUCD also has a declining trend.

FIGURE 6: Immunization service utilization

The trend in immunization shows that there was no immunization done from February 13, 2020 till April 12, 2020, but has an increasing trend in the second and third month of Lockdown. The number of TD vaccination decreased in the month of Chaitra (March 14, 2020- April 12, 2020) but has an increasing trend in the month of later months of lockdown (April 13, 2020- June 14, 2020).

IV. DISCUSSION

This study provides evidence of declining maternal health facilities utilization after nationwide lockdown due to COVID 19 outbreak. Antenatal care visits has been reduced to half. Cesarean and normal delivery, immunization and family planning follow decreasing trend. *The Lancet Global Health*, Timothy Robertson and colleagues report the indirect effect of COVID19 on maternal and child mortality using Lived Saved tools (LiST). They have created 3 scenarios in which they have showed different number of reduction in 4 component (availability of health worker, availability of supplies and equipment, demand of health service and access of health services) over period of 3, 6, 12 months. They estimated that with when there is a reduction of 39.3–51.9% and wasting increase up to 50% it will result in 56700 additional maternal death and 1157000 additional child death over 6 month period. This result would represent 9.8–44.7% increase in under-5 child deaths per month, and an 8.3–38.6% increase in maternal deaths per month.¹⁵ This study gives awareness about how disruption in maternal health service can increase the death count. From our study which shows decline in overall utilization of maternal health but it does not show cause of decline whether it is due to decrease in supply or demand of health services. But overall decline in maternal health services can have a serious impact on additional maternal and child death. Therefore Government should allocate health resources and manpower to intervention which can make a huge impact on ongoing crisis. Parental administration of uterotonics, antibiotics and anticonvulsant and clean birth environment would prevent death of 60% additional maternal death.¹⁵

V. CONCLUSION

Since the beginning of Lockdown, the utilization of ANC services, institutional deliveries has been on a declining trend. The utilization of temporary family planning services has shown an increasing trend on the month of Jestha (May 14, 2020- June 14,2020), whereas permanent family planning method has a declining trend. Immunization services, though was completely unused when COVID-19 began, has shown an increasing trend on the later months of Lockdown.

DISCLOSURE OF INTEREST

Since this study is self funded and no organization is involved, there is no disclosure of interest.

CONTRIBUTION TO AUTHORSHIP:

Sandhya Budhathoki: conceptualization, methodology, analysis **Bibhuti Adhikari:** original draft preparation, data collection, **Rupesh Ramtel:** writing, reviewing, editing.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study was approved by IRC of Nobel College.

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